

**THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MODERN
MEDICINE.**

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Abstract. It is difficult to imagine the modern world where the latest technologies appear without artificial intelligence. The development of artificial intelligence greatly facilitates the task of a person in various industries, including medicine. The emergence of artificial intelligence in medicine is the main reason for early diagnosis and effective treatment. This article details the role of artificial intelligence in current medicine.

Keywords. Artificial intelligence (AI), software products, diagnostics, treatment, advantage of artificial intelligence.

The term Artificial intelligence Artificial intelligence is the property of intelligent systems to perform creative functions that are traditionally considered the prerogative of a person (not to be confused with artificial creation); the science and technology of building intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs.

Spheres of use of artificial intelligence.

Applications and software products for recognition of medical images (MRI images, ultrasound findings, cardiograms, CT results); Start-ups for the development of drugs (microscopic analysis, study of the effectiveness of drugs, the study of viruses

and the search for effective vaccines); The use of machine learning technologies in the field of prosthetics (intelligent systems develop comfortable prostheses, taking into account the anatomical features of a person); Applications for remote patient care (they are popular in the UK - with their help general practitioners can remotely give recommendations for the treatment of colds or other conditions that are not life-threatening); Cancer treatment startups (eg SOPHiA AI, a \$30 million cancer diagnostics application that can analyze a patient's clinical picture and propose an effective treatment regimen)

Achievements of artificial intelligence.

At present, many programs have been developed in various branches of medicine to form diagnostics and treatment, determine risk groups in various diseases, etc. For example, China's AI program, which diagnoses childhood diseases as accurately as a doctor, may soon appear in clinics in China.

The program is able to analyze even handwritten notes, according to Medical Express. The researchers said that the artificial intelligence program combines the results of diagnosing some diseases better than doctors. The system consistently matched or outperformed primary care pediatricians in illnesses such as influenza, asthma, pneumonia, and meningitis. In addition, the program detects sinusitis as well as less common conditions with over 90% accuracy.

IBM develops systems in the field of oncology treatment. Also doing collaborative work with Johnson & Johnson in the field of research and treatment of chronic diseases. Microsoft is committed to developing the most effective drugs and treatments for cancer. The project includes analysis of medical images of tumors and mathematical analysis of cell development. Google's DeepMind platform is used. by the UK National Health Service to detect certain health risks based on data collected through mobile applications. The second project involves analyzing medical images from patients to develop "computer vision" algorithms for detecting cancerous tissue. Intel is developing AI programs that identify at-risk patients and suggest treatment options.

At the same time, the question arises: can artificial intelligence “overshadow” doctors? Only if it becomes more "human", which means that it is unlikely. Just like IBM's Watson, the system that diagnoses children actually reads and recognizes written notes from patient records filled out by regular doctors. The process of reviewing information is not much different from if the same records were reviewed by another doctor.

Like human doctors, during diagnosis, the AI categorized diseases by organ group (GI, upper or lower respiratory tract, etc.). The categories were then subdivided into smaller subcategories, as the machine mimicked the didactic thinking of a doctor who makes a diagnosis based on input data.

The advantage of AI in this study was that the amount of data provided for study, analysis and training was huge: more than a million outpatient visits and 600 thousand patients provided the neural network with 101 million data points for machine learning (MLC) classification. So artificial intelligence formed 55 different diagnoses by organ groups and subcategories.

The computer has surpassed junior pediatricians (with work experience from 3 to 15 years) in terms of diagnostic accuracy, but experienced specialists who have been working for more than 15 years, could not “win”.

Conclusion: In the future, as well as today, despite some concerns of doctors, machine doctors will not replace human doctors, but will only help them perform their duties more efficiently and quickly. China, as one of the main participants in the global intelligence race, has every chance to train neural networks faster than other countries. This is due to the fact that the confidentiality of personal data in this country is not high, and permission to analyze patient records can simply be obtained from the attending physicians.

Literature:

1. Ichimasa K, Kudo SE, Mori Y, Misawa M, Matsudaira S, Kouyama Y, et al. Artificial intelligence may help in predicting the need for additional surgery after endoscopic resection of T1 colorectal cancer. *Endoscopy*. (2018)

- 2.Sato F, Shimada Y, Selaru FM, Shibata D, Maeda M, Watanabe G, et al. Prediction of survival in patients with esophageal carcinoma using artificial neural networks. *Cancer*. (2005)
- 3.Steinhubl SR, Muse ED, Topol EJ. The emerging field of mobile health. *Sci Trans Med*. (2015)
- 4.Peng Y, Zhang Y, Wang L. Artificial intelligence in biomedical engineering and informatics: an introduction and review. *Artif Intell Med*. (2010)
- 5.Topol EJ. A decade of digital medicine innovation. *Sci Trans Med*. (2019)